

ISic3514

I.Sicily inscription 3514

Language

Latin

Type

funerary

Material

marble

Object

tabula

Editor

Jonathan Prag

Principal Contributor

Jonathan Prag

Contributors

Jonathan Prag,James Cummings,James Chartrand,Valeria Vitale,Michael Metcalfe,Simona Stoyanova

Autopsy

No Autopsy

Last Change

2020-11-26 - Simona Stoyanova restructured bibliography

Place of origin (ancient)

Messana

Place of origin (modern)

Messina

Provenance

Necropolis of San Placido

Coordinates

Current Location

Italy, Sicily, Messina, Museo regionale
interdisciplinare di Messina

Physical Description

Dimensions

Height cm

Width cm

Depth cm

Layout

Execution

Engraved

Letter Forms

Letter heights:

Line 1: mm

Interlineation

Interlineation line 1 to 2: mm

Text

Edition: EDR033621

1. [A]v[ia]llius [Via]
2. tor vi
3. xit ann o
4. XI.

Edition: PHI313630

1. [— — —]
2. [—]llius
3. [(e.g.) Via]tor²⁷[Vic]tor²⁷ vi-
4. xit □ an□n o [s]
5. XI.
- 6.

Apparatus

Translation

Commentary

Digital identifiers:

TM 284779

EDR 033621

PHI 313630

Bibliography

Bitto, I. 2001. Le iscrizioni greche e latine di Messina. *Pelorias* 7. Messina. At iii

Orsi, P. 1916. Messana. La necropoli romana di S. Placido e di altre scoperte avvenute nel 1910-1915. *Monumenti Antichi*. 24: 121-218. At 137

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